

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Employee Performance Evaluation System for Work Effectiveness at the Bone and Transmigration Office of the District of Bone Regency of South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted at the Regional Inspectorate of Bone Regency. This study aims to determine and analyze employee performance appraisal at the Bone and Transmigration Office of the District of Bone. As well as to find out and analyze the effectiveness of the work of employees at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration Bone Regency. To uncover these problems, the sampling in this study was purposive sampling. For data collection methods of observation, interviews and questionnaires were used. Analysis of the data used is a Likert scale by finding the average frequency (mean) and total average frequency (total mean). The results showed that the employee performance appraisal system at the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Bone Regency was largely determined by the knowledge, skills, attitudes, behavior of leadership. The effectiveness of the work of employees at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration Bone Regency is determined by the work skills possessed.

Keywords *Performance Appraisal, Work Effectiveness, Work.*

INTRODUCTION

Basically, performance appraisal is a key factor in developing an organization to achieve a high level of efficiency and work effectiveness, because individual performance appraisal is very beneficial for the dynamics of overall organizational growth through this appraisal, it can be seen the actual conditions of how employee performance. According to Niswaty et al., (2019) that in essence, the evaluation of individuals is the expected work in the form of an optimal performance and performance appraisal includes cooperation,

leadership, work quality, initiative, technical ability, enthusiasm, endurance/reliability, the quantity of work, and discipline.

Effective performance measurement according to the view (M. S. Saggaf et al., 2018) that the measure must be: (1) quantitative (2) easy to understand, (3) balanced, (4) easy to monitor, (5) often published. Furthermore (Achmad S. Ruky, 2002) said that the performance appraisal is comparing the actual results obtained with those planned. And for that, the evaluation of results or achievements themselves should not be left to superiors, but must be done by subordinates themselves should everyone be able to do it. According to Abdussamad et al., (2015), Nasila & Akib, (2014) stated that performance management is related to businesses, activities, or programs initiated by the leadership of the organization (company) to plan, direct and control employee performance. The factor- factors that affect the performance of education, skills or skills, and compensation.

Pratiwi et al., (2019) avers that a person's work performance or performance is influenced by three factors namely the ability to do his work, the level of effort, and support is given to that person. The relationship between these factors is widely recognized in the management literature, that in achieving one's work or work performance is the result of *abilities* multiplied by *effort* and multiplied by support. Where performance will decrease if one factor is reduced or eliminated.

Humans are the most important and decisive resource in efforts to achieve government success in development. No matter how perfect aspects of science and technology and economics without the quality aspects of human beings, it is difficult for government goals in development to be achieved optimally.

According to Saggaf et al., (2014), and Salam, (2015) stated that effectiveness is a condition that contains an understanding of the effects of the desired effect if a person who acts with a specific purpose that is desired, then people are said to be effective or cause a result or have a purpose as desired ". So it can be concluded that the effectiveness is seen by the two main factors contained therein, namely the existence of results or effects which are the results to achieve the desired goals.

Regional Personnel is a system and procedure regulated in-laws and regulations - at least covering planning, requirements, appointment, placement, education, and training, payroll, dismissal, retirement, coaching, position, rights, obligations, responsibilities, prohibitions, sanctions and awards are a sub-system of the national staffing system. Thus regional staffing is an integrated bureaucratic network within the national staff. When viewed in terms of quantity, the employees at the Bone Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office are sufficient.

But the reality that can be seen at certain hours is that several sections show the intensity of work that is lacking, or maybe they (employees) do not understand well what is the main task and function. Meanwhile, when viewed in terms of quality at the Bone Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office, it can be recognized that their quality still needs to be improved.

Based on the description above, it is deemed necessary to research to find out the efforts made by the local government to improve work effectiveness through improving the quality of human resources apparatus as has been done by (Ningsi et al., 2016; Nur,

2017; Septiana, 2013) under the title Work effectiveness of employees at PT. PLN (Persero) Medan North Sumatra Region has not been as expected, because it has not been supported by discipline and good employee performance appraisal. As data processing above, it shows that the influence of discipline and performance appraisal on the work effectiveness of employees at PT. PLN (Persero) Medan North Sumatra region has a very low influence, which can be seen from the results of the double correlation test (R) of 0.126. So it is done (Piggot-Irvine, 2003) The performance appraisal is carried out at the end of each year by the direct supervisor of each employee by comparing the targets in the planning and realization of achievements.

METHODS

This study uses descriptive qualitative analysis tools, by providing descriptions of each answer collected from the informants. The population of this study was employees of the Bone Manpower and Transmigration Office of 233 people consisting of 84 Civil Servants and 149 Honorary Workers. The number of samples is a representative of 45 civil servants and 45 honorary workers, then the total sample is 90 people. The source of data in this study consists of two, namely secondary data obtained from agencies related to the scope of this study, namely the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Bone Regency. The two primary data obtained directly from respondents in the form of information and responses of respondents relating to the variables of this study. Data collection techniques used in this study were observation, interviews, and questionnaires. The data analysis technique used in this study is to use a Likert scale to find the average frequency (mean) and total average frequency (total mean) (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Employee performance appraisal system

To provide an overview of the level of formal education and respondents, it can be seen in table 1.

Table 1

Frequency Distribution of Respondent Statements Regarding Formal Education Level of Employees in the Office of Manpower and Transmigration

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor degree	5	22	24,44
Strata Two	4	4	4.44
Diploma	3	2	2.22
SLTA	2	52	57.77
SD to SLTP	1	9	10
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements showed that in general, the Bone and Transmigration Manpower Office Staff had moderate educational

qualifications. This means that this needs to be addressed to continue to improve the educational qualifications of Employees within the scope of the Bone Manpower and Transmigration Office, both through study assignments and in the form of study permits. This is intended to improve basic competencies in increasing knowledge for employees through formal education.

The higher the level of one's formal education, the better level of knowledge, skills, and personality should be. Thus one indicator of the establishment of an organization in maintaining its existence in achieving the vision, mission, goals, and targets that have been set is to have human resources who have better knowledge, skills, and personalities, of the three things can be obtained in a structured manner through adequate formal education.

To find out whether the level of formal education influences the implementation of basic tasks and functions in the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Bone Regency, it can be seen in table 2

Table 2

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding the Effect of Formal Education Level on the Implementation of Main Tasks and Functions of Employees in the Office of Manpower and Transmigration

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very influential	5	42	46.66
Take effect	4	10	11,11
Less influential	3	30	33.33
No effect	2	8	8.88
Very no effect	1	0	0
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of respondents' statements shows that in general Employees at the Bone and Transmigration Office of Bone Regency stated that the level of a person's formal education influences the implementation of basic tasks and functions as a Civil Servant. This means that this shows how important it is to improve formal education qualifications for employees in supporting the implementation of basic tasks and daily functions. Because in carrying out daily tasks both routine and incidental, knowledge, skills, attitudes, and behavior are needed in carrying out these tasks.

To achieve organizational goals optimally, the existing human resources in the organization need to be empowered as well as possible in accordance with their abilities, expertise, and formal education. In connection with formal education, then an employee or employee should be placed in the field of duties and functions relevant to the formal education qualifications that he has obtained. This is in line with the principle of *the right man in the right place*.

To provide an overview of how each respondent's response to the relevance of formal education to the implementation of basic tasks and functions can be seen in table 3

Table 3

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding the Relevance between Formal Education Levels and Implementation of Main Tasks and Functions of Employees in the Office of Manpower and Transmigration

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very relevant	5	22	24.44
Relevant	4	52	57.77
Not relevant	3	11	12.2
Irrelevant	2	4	4.44
Very irrelevant	1	0	0
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of respondents' statements shows that in general Employees at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration stated that the level of formal education they had was quite relevant to the implementation of their main duties and functions as an Employee. This means that this indicates that the placement of Civil Servants in the Department of Manpower and Transmigration has paid attention to the type of formal education that is owned by employees at both levels and majors.

To find out the frequency of employee participation in the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in participating in Education and Training, it can be seen in table 4.

Table 4

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding Participation in Education and Training Activities

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
More than 10 times	5	22	24,44
7 to 9 times	4	4	4.44
5 to 6 times	3	2	2.22
3 to 4 times	2	52	57.77
Less than 2 times	1	9	10
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2016

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements shows that in general, the Employees at the Bone and Manpower Office of the District of Bone stated that their participation in the training activities was sufficient. This condition shows that the Bone Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office in terms of developing the human resources of the apparatus are getting enough attention.

The main objective and in education and training is to create a systematic process of changing employee behavior in a direction to improve organizational goals. In training an environment is created where employees can acquire or learn specific attitudes, abilities, expertise, knowledge, and behavior related to work. In the training given instructions to develop skills that can be directly used on the job. Education and training are based on the fact that an employee will need a growing set of knowledge, skills, and abilities in order to work well in the succession of positions he has encountered during his career.

To find out the influence of education and training programs on the implementation of the main duties and functions of Employees within the scope of the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, Bone Regency, can be seen in table 5.

Table 5

Frequency Distribution of Respondent Statements Regarding the Effect of Education and Training Programs on the Implementation of Main Tasks and Functions

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very influential	5	15	16.66
Take effect	4	35	38.88
Less influential	3	35	38.88
No effect	2	5	5.55
Very no effect	1	0	0
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of respondents' statements shows that in general, the Employees at the Bone and Manpower Office of the District of Bone stated that the education and training program that they had followed so far had quite an effect on the implementation of their main duties and functions as Employees. This shows that the education and training programs that have been followed can make a positive contribution to improving organizational effectiveness.

To find out whether the education and training program participated by Employees within the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Bone Regency is relevant to the main tasks and functions of the employees concerned, it can be seen in table 6

Table 6

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding the Relevance Between Education and Training Programs with Main Tasks and Functions

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very relevant	5	52	57.77
Relevant	4	4	4.44
Not relevant	3	23	25.55
Irrelevant	2	11	12.22
Very irrelevant	1	0	10

Amount		90	100
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Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of respondents' statements shows that in general Employees at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration stated that the education and training programs that they had followed up to now were quite relevant to the implementation of their main duties and functions as Employees.

To find out the frequency of attendance at the office on average each month for employees within the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration, Bone Regency, see table 7.

Table 7

Frequency Distribution of Respondent Statements Regarding the Frequency of Attendance at the Office on an Average Each Month

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
More than 25 days	5	30	33.33
Between 20 to 24 days	4	52	57.77
Between 15 to 19 days	3	8	8.88
Between 10 to 14 days	2	0	0
Less than 9 days	1	0	0
Amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements shows that in general, the Employees at the Bone and Transmigration Office of Bone Regency have shown a fairly high level of attendance. This needs to be maintained if necessary it can be further enhanced.

Another important thing related to attitudes and behavior is the relationship or communication between individuals or individuals in the organization. Interpersonal communication is behavior-oriented, so the emphasis is on the process of delivering information and one person to another person. In this case, communication is seen as a fundamental way to influence behavior change, and which unites psychological processes such as perception, understanding, and motivation on the one hand with language on the other. To find out the relationship or communication between fellow subordinates (horizontal relations) can be seen in table 8.

Table 8

Frequency Distribution of Respondent Statements Regarding Relationships Between Subordinates (Horizontal Relations)

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very good	5	15	16.66
Good	4	5	5.55

Not good	3	35	38.88
Not good	2	35	38.88
Very bad	1	0	0
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed, 2019

The frequency distribution of respondents' statements shows that in general, the relationship between fellow subordinates for employees within the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Bone Regency has been going quite well. But there are still some respondents who claim that the relationship between them horizontally is still not going well. This is what needs to be minimized as early as possible before things that are not conducive occur.

In addition to the relationship between subordinates (horizontal relations), the other relationship that is quite important in an organization is the relationship between superiors and subordinates (vertical relations). A superior cannot impose an understanding of his subordinates. But what he can do is to form a communication situation framework by fostering an atmosphere that gives rise to understanding. To do this, he must first know what is desired in communication. The leader must plan communication, then he must make the information in accordance with the language and frame of his subordinates. Thus the information must bring understanding because it is conveyed through language symbols that are familiar to the recipient. In other words, the language used to convey information is known by the recipient so that an atmosphere of mutual understanding grows.

To find out the relationship or communication between superiors and subordinates (vertical relationship) within the scope of the Bone Manpower and Transmigration Office can be seen in table 9.

Table 9

Frequency Distribution of Respondent Statements Regarding Relationship between Superiors and Subordinates (Vertical Relations)

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very good	5	16	17.77
Good	4	30	33.33
Not good	3	14	15.55
Not good	2	30	33.33
Very bad	1	0	0
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed, 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements shows that in general, the relationship between superiors and subordinates for employees within the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration in Bone Regency was quite good. However, there were still some respondents who stated that the relationship between them vertically

was still unfavorable. This also needs to be minimized as early as possible before things that are not conducive occur.

To find out the motivation given by leaders to subordinates in the scope of the Office of Manpower and Transmigration, Bone Regency can be seen in table 10.

Table 10

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statement Regarding Submission of Motivation and Leadership to Subordinates

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Always	5	52	57.77
Often	4	9	10.00
Sometimes	3	7	7.77
Ever	2	22	24.44
Never	1	0	0
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed, 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements shows that in general, the leadership element in the Bone and Transmigration Office of the District of Bone had sufficient motivation to increase work effectiveness for the employees.

In carrying out the main tasks and daily functions, a subordinate may not do it alone but must do according to applicable regulations to achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently. With regard to these conditions, the role of a leader in providing guidance/guidance is very necessary to reduce the occurrence of errors both technically and procedurally. Guidance/guidance provided by the leadership is a follow-up and provisions or rules that have not been detailed or something that can provide multiple meanings in its implementation.

To find out whether the leadership element within the scope of the Bone Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office provides guidance/guidance in the implementation of basic tasks and daily functions, it can be seen in table 11.

Table 11

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding Provision of Guidance / Guidance and Lead (Direct Supervisor) to Subordinates

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Always	5	12	13.33
Often	4	16	17.77
Sometimes	3	52	57.77
Ever	2	10	11,11
Never	1	0	0
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed, 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements shows that in general, the leadership element in the Bone and Transmigration Office of the District of Bone had sufficiently provided guidance/instructions to their subordinates in terms of carrying out basic tasks and functions. This shows that every employee has a great responsibility to improve the effectiveness of the organization's work. These responsibilities are formed hierarchically based on their respective authorities.

To find out whether the leadership element has given a good role model to their subordinates, it can be seen in table 12.

Table 12

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statements Regarding Leadership Leadership Model

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Always	5	12	13.33
Often	4	22	24.44
Sometimes	3	11	12.22
Ever	2	45	50.00
Never	1	0	0
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

The frequency distribution of the respondents' statements showed that in general, the leadership element in the Bone and Transmigration Department of the Bone Regency had sufficiently provided a good example to their subordinates.

Employee Work Effectiveness

To measure the effectiveness of the work of employees in the scope of the Department of Manpower and Transmigration of Bone Regency, the indicators used are completion of tasks on target, completion of tasks on time, and minimal error rate. To find out the level of effectiveness of Employees' work within the scope of the Bone Manpower and Transmigration Office, which is an accumulation of the four indicators, it can be seen in table 13.

Table 13

Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Statement Recognizing the Effectiveness of Employees in the Scope of the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Bone Regency

Category	Score	Frequency	Percentage
Very good	5	52	57.77
Good	4	22	24.44
Is	3	2	2.22

Bad	2	4	4.44
Very bad	1	9	10
amount		90	100

Source: Primary data processed in 2019

From the frequency distribution of the respondents' statements indicate that in general, the Employees at the Office of Manpower and Transmigration in Bone District have relatively good work effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion that have been presented in the previous section, the conclusions can be drawn as follows: 1) The employee performance appraisal system at the Bone and Transmigration Office of Bone Regency is very much determined by the knowledge, skills, attitudes, behaviors of leadership, 2) The effectiveness of employees' work at the Bone Regency Manpower and Transmigration Office is determined by their work skills.

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